

STUDIES ON THE POTENTIOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF ASCORBIC ACID IN FRUIT AND VEGETABLE EXTRACTS

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A satisfactory potentiometric procedure for the determination of the ascorbic acid content of fruit and vegetable extracts, using a Hg-Pt electrode, has been described

The titrimetric determination of ascorbic acid with 2:6-dichlorophenol indophenol, originally suggested by Tillmans (*Untersuch. Lebensm.*, 1927, 54, 33) and later modified by Bessey and King (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, 103, 687), is the most widely used method to-day. This method has been adapted to the photometric determination of ascorbic acid, a method not quite suited for highly pigmented and turbid extracts. To meet such difficulties a potentiometric method with special Hg—Pt double electrode was suggested (Harris *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1942, 36, 183) but the electrode tended to become sluggish in concentrated extracts. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to evolving a satisfactory potentiometric procedure for the determination of ascorbic acid content of fruit and vegetable extracts.

EXPERIMENTAL

A saturated calomel electrode with a KCl-agar salt bridge was used as a reference electrode and the titrations were carried out in CO₂-atmosphere. Potential measurements were made with a Verbier potentiometer.

Gold-coated, mercury-coated and silver-coated platinum electrodes as well as bright and platinised platinum electrodes were used so as to select the most suitable electrode among these for the accurate estimation of ascorbic acid.

All solutions were prepared as prescribed in "Methods of Vitamins Assay" (1951). The fruit and vegetable extracts were prepared as described by Bessey and King (*loc. cit.*).

The platinum electrode, in general, was found to take a long time to attain equilibrium, and a continuous drift of potential was noticed during the titration. The silver-coated platinum electrode was found unsuitable in these titrations, since no point of inflexion was observable in the curves (Fig. 1).

A rod-type platinum electrode, coated with a thin layer of mercury, was observed to respond well to each addition of the dye in ascorbic acid solutions, stabilised with oxalic or metaphosphoric acid.

The influence of the time of electroplating on the maximum increase of potential at the end-point for the addition of 0.05 c. c. of the dye (0.025%) was first studied. The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Behaviour of the Hg-coated Pt electrode under diff. conditions.
Time for attaining equilibrium: $\approx$ 1min.

No.	Time of electroplating the electrode.	* Max. increase in potential.	Visual.	End-point.		% Diff.
				From the curve.		
1	30 sec.	28 mv	8.0 c.c.	7.95 c.c.	0.6	
2	" (with KCl)	36	8.0	8.00	0.0	
3	45	29	8.0	7.95	0.6	
4	" (Do)	38	8.0	8.00	0.0	
5	2 mins.	15	8.0	7.95	0.6	
6	" (Do)	18	8.0	7.95	0.6	
7	10	13	8.0	7.95	0.6	
8	" (Do)	16	8.0	7.95	0.6	
9	30	15	8.0	7.90	1.25	
10	" (Do)	15	8.0	7.90	1.25	

* For 0.05 c.c. of the dye.

FIG. I

As seen from Table I, a better response is observable with a very thin coating of mercury on the electrode ; an electrode, coated with mercury for 45 seconds, gives the maximum increase in potential (29 mv) and this increase is enhanced to 38 mv when a small amount (0.1 c.c.) of saturated potassium chloride is present. Further, the addition of potassium chloride has a stabilising effect on the E.M.F. These observations support the theory of Harris *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) that the Hg-Pt electrode behaves as a mercury electrode, but when an excess of the dye is present, the metallic mercury changes to Hg^{2+} ions and the electrode behaves as a platinum electrode.

A platinum electrode with a thick coating of gold responded satisfactorily in these titrations. The inflexion at the end-point for the addition of 0.05 c.c. (0.025%) of the dye solution was found to be 20 mv.

The stabilising medium, either oxalic or metaphosphoric acid, was not found to have any significant influence on the nature of the curves obtained with the different electrodes.

The dye solution (0.025%) after standardisation by titration with standard ascorbic acid (1 mg. in 10 c.c. of 3% metaphosphoric acid) can satisfactorily be used for the determination of the ascorbic acid content of fruit and vegetable extracts.

TABLE II

Comparison of values of ascorbic acid obtained with Hg-Pt and gold-plated platinum electrodes.

No.	Name of fruit of vegetable.	Hg—Pt electrode.		Gold electrode.	
		End-point from the curve.	Ascorbic acid (mg./100 g.).	End-point from the curve.	Ascorbic acid (mg./100 g.).
1	Orange juice	6.60 c.c.	24.0*	6.55 c.c.	23.8*
2	Tomato	7.90	28.7	7.85	28.6
3	Onion	3.85	14.0	3.85	14.0
4	Mint leaves	22.85	83.1	22.65	82.4
5	Spinach leaves	12.65	46.0	12.55	45.6

* The ascorbic acid content is given in mg / 100 c.c. of the juice.

From the results Hg—Pt double electrode appears to be a satisfactory electrode for the determination of ascorbic acid ; however, a gold electrode can also be used as an alternate electrode where a check on the Hg—Pt electrode becomes necessary.

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